

A novel bioluminescent bacteria-based method coupled with dynamic time warping for detecting and differentiating copper and mercury in water

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ABSTRACT

The present study offers a new method for analyzing the bioluminescence kinetics generated by the toxicity-triggered bioluminescent bacterial mutant strain TV1061 to detect and differentiate heavy metals in water samples. Specifically, as a proof-of-concept, copper and mercury were used, in single and binary mixtures, to induce the *grpE* heatshock promoter generating a measurable signal. The research employed the Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) algorithm to analyze the overall bioluminescence signal generated by the bacteria, rather than focusing on specific signal components, such as the response ratio. The method demonstrated high accuracy in classifying the samples (94 % accuracy). This technique is a first stepping stone in creating a database that will enable to accurately identify mixtures of toxicants and predict their concentration in the sample. This approach is reliable, cost-effective, and rapid for monitoring and assessing toxic contaminants in water, including deciphering distinct recognition patterns, such as for copper and mercury (our chosen case specimens), including in binary mixtures, highlighting its potential for the precise identification and quantification of heavy metals in complex mixtures. Our findings support the possibility of developing a larger dataset of multiple references for multiple heavy metals and other toxicants, that will improve the overall detection capabilities of our system, all this thanks to the combined use of data mining and machine learning techniques.

1. Introduction

Heavy metals are one of the most dangerous classes of toxicants because they are carcinogenic and tend to accumulate (Kadim and Risjani 2022). Heavy metals enter the food chain through direct absorption by organisms that populate water. Thus, their presence in water must be monitored qualitatively and quantitatively. While methods such as Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) and Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) provide highly sensitive and specific detection of heavy metals, they require expensive instrumentation, extensive sample preparation, and are not suitable for rapid, in-field analysis or only testing (McGeehan et al., 2020; Pan et al. 2020). Similarly, emerging biosensor technologies, including cell-free aptamer-based sensors, offer promising real-time detection but often focus on single analytes and lack the ability to analyze complex mixtures or dynamic response kinetics (Xue et al. 2020). In addition, these methods

cannot assess the biological effects of these toxic analytes.

The novel direction of analysis is toward sensors, namely biosensors and chemical sensors, as well as *in vivo* detection (Azmi et al. 2018). Bacterial bioreporters provide the bioavailability and bioaccessibility of a wide spectrum of compounds and constitute an excellent tool for monitoring toxicity (Robbens et al. 2010). Bioluminescent *Escherichia coli*-based bioassays have been employed successfully to assess the toxicity of pure compounds and some mixtures, and a lot of know-how was gained on the molecular mode of action of both new and existing chemicals. Moreover, this model can be applied to complex environmental mixtures. The available knowledge on the actual performance of bioreporters in terms of variability, detection limit, repeatability, selectivity, and specificity has been standardized as a general method. The bacterial response to tested samples as a marker of toxicity proved to be a fairly fast, sensitive, and a reliable method (Zeng et al. 2021). However, one of the challenges of these biological models that require

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further research is the ability of the system to detect constituents from mixtures of compounds. Several methods (Wang et al. 2020) have been proposed to address this issue, and while some techniques have been successful in detecting heavy metals, the problem of identifying mixtures remains an active topic.

Advancements in machine learning have offered new opportunities to update and enhance the processes involved in deciphering bacterial bioluminescence generated from bioassays for toxicity monitoring. The predominant method for bioluminescent bacterial detection employs different promoters to activate the lux operon for bioluminescence production, with specific compounds triggering measurable signals (Holmes et al. 1994).

Calculated indices, such as the response ratio (induction factor), help to determine the level of toxicity without providing a clear identification of the toxicant (Lior et al. 2018). This issue is even more difficult to solve for mixtures of toxicants. To investigate these mixtures, several studies have used half-maximal effective concentrations (EC₅₀ values) to quantify the concentration causing a 50 % reduction in light emission based on concentration-response relationships (Holmes et al. 1994; Lior et al. 2018; Mansour et al. 2015; Wang et al. 2020). However, in the current study, the recombinant bioluminescent bacteria is a type of “lights on” system, and bioluminescence was induced by the heavy metal samples (Belkin 2025). Other studies have revealed that mixture components can interact in various ways (antagonistically, additively, independently, or synergistically), posing challenges for component identification (Plackett and Hewlett 1952). To address this, mathematical approaches have been developed to analyze bioluminescence. These techniques include the isobologram method for multi-component mixtures, response surface methods using multiple linear regression, and toxic unit methods that quantify the contribution of each constituent to the overall effect (Berenbaum 1981; Fulladosa et al. 2005; Gao et al. 2016; Ince et al. 1999; Loewe and Muischnek 1926; Mansour et al. 2015; Plackett and Hewlett 1952; Sanchís et al. 2016; Zeb et al. 2017). Some studies have attempted to virtualize the environment for toxicity bioassays using advanced methods, such as Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship (Hansch et al. 1962) and Predictive Decision Tree Models, including the CHAID algorithm (Fulladosa et al. 2005; Jouanneau et al. 2011; Sprague and Ramsay 1965), with limited results.

However, existing techniques often overlook the similarities between sample kinetics and multiple references. The primary issue occurs when only the response ratio is calculated, because this approach fails to differentiate between signals with multiple peaks, given that only the highest peak is considered. This limitation can be addressed by aligning the entire signal with the reference signal. Unlike these conventional approaches, analyses based solely on response ratios or peak intensities miss temporal information from bioluminescent responses. To understand these data, computational methods such as machine learning algorithms that analyze entire kinetic profiles can significantly improve discrimination between different toxicants, especially in complex mixtures. To enhance the discrimination between toxicants in water, we propose an unsupervised learning-based approach utilizing nearest neighbor classifiers with dynamic time warping (DTW) (Fraser 1872; Senin 2008). This computational method accurately compares sequences with varying timing and speeds, making it suitable for analyzing time-series data with similar patterns yet different durations (Bliss 1939; EPA 2000; Itakura 1975; Luzianin and Krause 2016). The application of DTW to bioluminescence data allows for an accurate comparison of the complex temporal variations influenced by several factors, including the presence of metals and environmental conditions.

In this study, we used dynamic time-warping-based classification to analyze bioluminescent kinetic fingerprints, providing accurate discrimination and quantification capabilities that exceed traditional response-based methods. A specific strain of bioluminescent bacteria genetically equipped with the lux operon fused to the *grpE* promoter was used for the bioassay. These bacteria were exposed to control samples as well as to known concentrations of heavy metals, which served as

reference samples. The collected data were analyzed using DTW to compute the distances between the sample bioluminescence profiles and reference profiles. By comparing these distances, the samples were classified based on their similarity to the references, with lower distances indicating higher similarity. This process allows for the precise classification and identification of toxic compounds in water samples, offering a new, efficient, and sensitive method for classifying bioluminescence kinetics.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. The source of bacteria samples

The bioluminescent bacterium used was *E. coli* strain TV1061 (strain host RFM443, which contains a plasmid-borne fusion of the *grpE* promoter (Arsène et al. 2000) to the reporter operon *grpE::luxCDABE* (Dyk et al. 1994)). The choice of this strain was based on its sensitivity to heatshock and metabolic changes in the cytoplasm, which correspond to the produced bioluminescence. This strain can react with a large number of toxicants, including several heavy metals, in water. Metals such as copper and mercury can induce cellular stress, activating heat-shock promoters that initiate the expression of stress response genes. This activation can lead to the increased expression of bioluminescent genes, resulting in higher light emission in metal-exposed bacteria. Conversely, in double distilled water (DDW), bacterial metabolism remains relatively inactive, producing lower bioluminescence signals because there are no external stimuli prompting stress responses or gene activation. Therefore, the increased luminescence observed in the presence of metals reflects cellular stress or metabolic activation associated with toxicant exposure rather than toxicity inhibition alone.

The plasmid-borne fusion of the *grpE* promoter to the reporter operon *luxCDABE* found in strain TV1061 is responsible for the synthesis of the luciferase units (lux A and B) and for the synthesis of the luciferase substrate by an ATP- and NADPH-dependent multi-enzyme complex composed of fatty acid reductase, transferase, and a synthetase (lux C, D, and E) (Meighen 1993).

2.2. Bacteria cultivation conditions

The stock culture was activated by inoculating agar containing Luria Bertani agar Difco (244,520) and ampicillin (100 µg/mL). The plates were incubated overnight at 37 °C and stored in a refrigerator at 4 °C for a maximum period of 30 days to ensure that the bacteria did not reject the plasmids. A working liquid culture was prepared from the activated culture by inoculating 20 mL of Luria-Bertani broth with ampicillin (10 µg/mL). The tubes were incubated overnight at 37 °C with continuous shaking at 150 rpm. Finally, a new liquid culture was prepared from the overnight culture, without antibiotics, to ensure that there was no stress on the bacteria. After the exponential growth phase was reached, the inoculum concentration was determined by measuring the optical density at 600 nm, and 90 µL was transferred into 96-well microtiter plates (Nunc, Denmark) for further measurements.

2.3. The preparation of single and binary mixtures of copper and mercury in water

Samples of copper and mercury were prepared in the lab using an analytical balance to weigh their respective salts and dissolve them in double distilled water (DDW). First, salts of Cu and Hg samples were used. The reaction of the bacteria was tested on a linear dilution, where the concentration of the metal increased by the same absolute value, starting from 0.001 mg/mL up to 1 mg/mL (Table 1). Second, mixtures of the two heavy metals were prepared to evaluate their interactions with the bacteria. The first mixture consisted of copper (1 mg/mL), whose concentration was constant, and mercury, which was prepared in a linear dilution of concentrations (from 0.001 mg/mL up to 1 mg/mL),

Table 1
Heavy metals and their concentrations.

Single HM	Concentrations mg/mL			Number of samples
Cu	0.001, 0.002, 0.003, ..., 0.01, 0.02, ..., 0.1, 0.2, ..., 1			28
Hg	0.001, 0.002, 0.003, ..., 0.01, 0.02, ..., 0.1, 0.2, ..., 1			28
Heavy metal 1 (HM1)	Heavy metal 2 (HM2)	Concentration HM1:HM2 mg/mL (from)	Concentration HM1:HM2 mg/mL (to)	Number of samples
Cu	Hg	0.5: 0.0005	0.5:0.5	28
Hg	Cu	0.5: 0.0005	0.5:0.5	28

*Extended table can be found in supplementary material S1.

resulting in 28 samples. The second type of mixture consisted of mercury and copper, where mercury was at a constant concentration and copper increased in concentration, resulting in an additional 28 samples. In addition, 27 samples of double distilled water were tested to check the variations in bioluminescence (negative control), resulting in a total of 139 samples.

2.4. The bioluminescence kinetics

The bioluminescence kinetics were recorded with a Luminoskan Ascent luminometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, United States) over a period of 6 h, with measurements every 5 min. The samples were exposed to bacteria in white 96-well microtiter plates containing 90 μ L of bacterial culture and 10 μ L of heavy metal samples (Fig. 1). Each sample was tested in triplicate, and nine wells were used as controls. Double-distilled water (DDW) was used as the negative control, whereas ethanol was used as a positive control (2 % and 5 %).

2.5. The DTW algorithm for pattern recognition

DTW is an algorithm that measures the similarity between two temporal sequences. A detailed description can be found in the specific

literature (Cassisi et al. 2012). Before implementing the algorithm, it is essential to consider the features of the biological signal (Fig. 2). The signal consists of a unique, aperiodic, non-linear pattern, with several peaks suggesting non-stationarity. The graph depicts a monotonic increasing or decreasing trend in peaks over time, which reflects the bacterial metabolism and reaction to toxicants by the activation of the heat-shock promoter. For this purpose, the matching capabilities of the DTW algorithm can identify pattern similarities better than other techniques.

The DTW algorithm was implemented for pattern recognition using bioluminescence time-series data generated by bacteria exposed to varying concentrations of copper and mercury. The analysis process included the collection of bioluminescence time-series data. The bioluminescence response of the bacteria over time was continuously recorded using a luminometer to generate time-series data. Triplicate wells were used to ensure that no significant variations were found. DTW was then applied to compare the time-series data for each exposure condition. The algorithm works by warping the time dimension of each series to find an optimal alignment between them, allowing for a more accurate comparison than the simple Euclidean distance (Yadav and Alam 2018). It calculates a distance matrix between the points in the two time series and then finds the path through this matrix that minimizes the total distance (Senin, 2008). This warping path represents the best alignment of the two time series achieved by stretching and shrinking until the test signal matches the reference signal as optimally as possible (Keogh and Pazzani 2001; Luzianin and Krause 2016; Rabiner et al. 1978). This warping path represents the best alignment of the two time series and is given by the simplified formula:

$$DTW \text{ distance} = \sum^{sequence} error$$

Once the DTW distances are calculated, they can be used for pattern recognition. In this study, these distances were used to classify the bioluminescence responses according to the concentrations of copper and mercury. This was achieved by comparing the bioluminescence data of the samples with those of multiple references (Fig. 2). Satisfactory

Fig. 1. Protocol used for detection of copper and mercury with bioluminescent bacteria (created with BioRender.com).

Fig. 2. Bioluminescence kinetics for A: reference 1 (double distilled water); reference 2 (copper), reference 3 (mercury); B: reference 4 (copper with mercury), reference 5 (mercury with copper).

results were achieved by choosing five references, namely double distilled water (reference 1), copper (0.9 mg/mL – reference 2), mercury (0.9 mg/mL – reference 3), copper with mercury (0.5:0.0005 mg/mL – reference 4), and lastly mercury with copper (0.5:0.0005 mg/mL – reference 5). The final step involved evaluating the performance of DTW-based pattern recognition by calculating its accuracy.

2.6. Statistical analyses and software used to interpret the results

The bioluminescence kinetics recorded by the Luminoskan machine were analyzed using Microsoft Excel. For each experimental condition, three replicate measurements of bioluminescence kinetics were obtained. These replicates were assessed for consistency using the coefficient of variation (CV). Any replicate showing a response that was >20 % different from the mean of the triplicates was flagged as a potential outlier. Replicates identified as outliers were excluded, and the remaining data were averaged to obtain a representative kinetic profile. If two or more replicates were considered outliers, the entire measurement was discarded, and the experiment was repeated to ensure data reliability. The acceptable variance among the triplicates was maintained below 10 % to ensure reliable and reproducible results. The algorithm for data analysis was written in Python Software Foundation, Python Language Reference version 3.8.

3. Results

3.1. Bioluminescence kinetics of heavy metals and references selection

All samples containing double distilled water (DDW) were evaluated for variability. Sample number 13 was chosen as the reference because it exhibited the lowest bioluminescence response among all the DDW samples. Number 13 demonstrates the lowest response, ensuring that the reference profile closely represents minimal bioluminescence activity, which is important for discriminating between true toxic effects and background variability. The DTW algorithm successfully classified all 27 samples by comparing their distances with this reference.

The distribution of distances from all DDW samples to the reference is shown in Fig. 3. As expected, the smallest distance (indicating the highest similarity) was zero for the reference itself, and the maximum distance among DDW samples was 48.69. The average distance from the reference across all DDW samples was 19.36, with a standard deviation of 9.39, highlighting variability within the negative control group.

Furthermore, copper and mercury were classified using the DTW technique by choosing three references: reference 1 was double distilled water (DDW), reference 2 was copper 0.9 mg/mL, and mercury 0.9 mg/mL served as reference 3 (Table 2).

The distances between these references and the samples were then

Fig. 3. DDW distances scatter plot. When DTW distances are calculated, they provide a high resolution for discrimination.

Table 2

Calculated distances for references using the DTW algorithm.

Ref.	Cu mg/mL	Hg	Distance to DDW	Distance to Cu	Distance to Hg	Distance to the mixture of Cu:Hg	Distance to the mixture of Hg:Cu
DDW	–	–	0	184.69	117.55	245.81	256.24
Cu	0.9	–	184.69	0	182.67	200.24	249.49
Hg	–	0.9	117.55	182.67	0	318.67	235.94
Cu:Hg	0.5	0.0005	245.81	200.24	318.67	0	301.52
Cu:Hg	0.0005	0.5	256.24	249.49	235.94	301.52	0

*supplementary material with all samples and references can be found separately (S2).

calculated. If the distance between the sample and any reference is closer to 0, it means that they are alike; in other words, the closer to the reference values a sample is, the more similar they are. For example, the sample of water chosen as reference 1 has a distance to reference 1 (DDW) of 0 (comparing to itself), a distance to reference 2 (copper 0.9 mg/mL) of 184.96, and a distance to reference 3 (mercury 0.9 mg/mL) of 117.55 (Table 2). Similarly, if we compare it to the mixture references, it has a distance to a mixture of Cu:Hg 0.5:0.0005 mg/mL (reference 4) of 245.81 and a distance to a mixture of Hg:Cu 0.5:0.0005 mg/mL (reference 5) of 256.24. From these calculated distances, it can be concluded that the tested sample was closer to reference 1 (DDW) because it had the lowest value (0). Similarly, for the sample of copper chosen as reference (copper 0.9 mg/mL, reference 2), the distance to reference 1 (DDW) is 184.69, to reference 2 (copper 0.9 mg/mL) is 0, to reference 3 (mercury 0.9 mg/mL) is 182.67, to reference 4 (Cu:Hg 0.5:0.0005 mg/mL) is 200.24, and to reference 5 (Hg:Cu 0.5:0.0005 mg/mL) is 249.49. From these calculations, it can be concluded that the analyzed sample was copper. The algorithm correctly classified 27 of the 28 copper samples and 23 of the 28 mercury samples.

Similarly, mixtures of copper and mercury were classified. After calculating the distances to all references, the algorithm correctly classified 54 of the 56 samples. Two samples (Cu:Hg 0.5:0.5 mg/mL and Cu:Hg 0.5:0.45) were not classified correctly. For mixtures of Hg:Cu, the results were completely accurate, with all 56 samples out of 56 classified correctly.

When an unknown sample is analyzed, its bioluminescent kinetics are compared with those of all references, and the lowest distance is chosen for labeling. Additionally, the algorithm can automatically identify a sample based on its bioluminescent kinetics. For example,

after measuring the distance of an unknown sample to reference 1, and the distance is higher than 48.69, the algorithm will choose the next reference. The number 48.69 is the threshold value because it is the highest value recorded for water. Similarly, after measuring the distance to reference 2, and this time higher than 105.84, the algorithm will move on to reference 3 (threshold 110.45), reference 4 (130.51), and finally, reference 5 (199.41). The algorithm labels the sample after selecting the lowest distance to a reference. This requires a relatively high amount of computational power, especially when analyzing big datasets with a higher number of references.

The scatter plot illustrating the Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) distances of all samples relative to each reference is shown in Fig. 4. This visualization facilitates the identification of patterns, clusters, or anomalies within the dataset by comparing samples to established reference points using the DTW distance metric.

3.2. Estimation of the components in the solution

In addition to identifying the heavy metals in the sample, the proposed method was able to provide an essential dataset that we used to train and predict the concentration of heavy metals in the samples (Fig. 5).

First, it is important to note that the bioluminescence kinetics were highly variable among the concentrations of the samples, and the prediction of the concentration required further refinement to achieve satisfactory results. In order to improve the accuracy of the estimation of the concentration in the samples, 10 samples from each type were used for training, and the remaining 18 samples were used to predict their concentrations. We used the Gradient Boosting (GB) as the training

Fig. 4. Scatter plot of the DTW distances of all samples to each reference.

algorithm and was based on the calculated DTW distances (ATLAS Collaboration 2014, Nigusie et al. 2024).

Gradient Boosting (GB) is a versatile machine learning approach that can be adapted to various datasets, including the specialized case where DTW distances are calculated (Rizkallah 2025). By employing GB

alongside the calculation of DTW distances, we improved the prediction of all classes.

In the context of time-series regression, the use of DTW to measure the similarity or dissimilarity between time-series data points creates a dataset for further analysis. This information then serves as an input

Fig. 5. Predicted concentrations of metals in the four types of samples (A): copper, (B): mercury, (C): copper in mixtures of Hg:Cu, (D): mercury in mixtures of Cu:Hg.

feature for the Gradient Boosting model. The model can then learn complex patterns and relationships by exploiting these DTW-based features, such that, in our case, 10 points from each sample type were sufficient to train and predict future concentrations with high accuracy. The GB builds a series of decision trees, one after the other. Each new tree attempts to fix the mistakes made by the previous ones. In this way, the model gradually improves at predicting the new points. By using the DTW distances, the model can better handle the complexities of time-sequence data, leading to more accurate predictions.

The detection of copper concentrations was the lowest, resulting in $R^2 = 0.88$. This could be explained by the high variability in the responses, where the sample containing 0.04 mg/mL had the highest variation in the dataset. Mercury achieved $R^2 = 0.92$, with a more uniform dataset.

Both types of mixtures achieved >95 % accuracy (Cu in Hg:Cu samples $R^2 = 0.98$ and Hg in Cu:Hg $R^2 = 0.95$). The fixed components were estimated with high accuracy as well. Interestingly, the mixtures were closer to the copper reference than the mercury reference, even though the kinetics of copper are highly variable. This implies that the bacteria react differently to Cu, possibly due to different mechanisms of resistance to heavy metals. Overall, mercury had a lower induction of bioluminescence compared to copper; however, when mixed together, the bioluminescence was highly increased. By simply using only one type of reference, it is not possible to accurately predict the concentration in a mixture. Nevertheless, only one type of reference was able to predict that the unknown samples were most likely composed of a mixture of toxicants.

4. Discussion

In this study, a new method for analyzing the bioluminescence kinetics generated by the bioluminescent bacterial mutant strain TV1061 for the detection of constituents of single and binary mixtures of heavy metals in water was presented. Although several strains of bioluminescent bacteria have been created with unique promoters that are activated by heavy metals (Ivask et al. 2009), the goal of this study was to show that data analysis with advanced algorithms can significantly improve the spectrum of toxicants that can be detected by screening using bioluminescent bioreporter bacteria with non-specific promoters, including differentiation from mixtures thereof.

The technique used, namely DTW, for the classification of bioluminescence kinetics has a different approach than the reported methods because it considers the entire signal pattern rather than isolated peaks, which makes it more effective in distinguishing responses caused by different toxicants, including their combinations. DTW has been proven to be more efficient in discriminating between heavy metals in water. When DTW distances deviate significantly from the DDW reference, toxicity is indicated, similar to an increased response ratio. Additionally, by analyzing the raw data generated by the bioluminescent bacteria, good results were achieved in discriminating heavy metals by choosing only five references. Moreover, this technique allows the use of unlimited references at the cost of computational power, while possibly improving accuracy.

Biological responses, such as the activation of heat-shock promoters, serve as sensitive indicators of cellular stress induced by toxicants, such

as heavy metals. When bacteria are exposed to stress, specific gene expression pathways are triggered, resulting in altered bioluminescence kinetics. Analyzing these kinetic patterns, especially the activation and suppression sequences, allows not only the detection but also the differentiation of toxicants within mixtures. Our method leverages this biological response using advanced algorithms to recognize distinct bioluminescent fingerprints associated with individual components and their synergistic effects in complex matrices.

The bioluminescence kinetics changed differently for each metal, demonstrating that Cu and Hg have different fingerprints. For copper, the signal tended to increase overall compared with mercury, where it tended to decrease in the first two peaks and increase in the third peak compared with the water reference. Both types of binary mixtures exhibited a reduced overall signal and an increase in the last peak. This effect can be explained by the fact that copper and mercury have different modes of action on bacteria and together have a synergistic effect compared to their individual effects (Helbig et al. 2008; Williams and Silver 1984). The method applied in this study enables grouping the distances of the samples into ranges such that when an unknown sample is analyzed, it can easily be classified into the established library. The disparity of the points is quite scattered for single elements compared with the mixtures. However, our classification approach correctly identified 94 % of the samples, demonstrating the efficacy of the DTW method in discriminating between different heavy metals and mixtures. Variability in distances reflects the biological complexity at lower concentrations, but overall, the method remains accurate.

The proposed method successfully identified the heavy metals in water samples and provided an essential dataset for training and predicting their concentrations. Despite variable bioluminescence kinetics among sample concentrations, the accuracy of concentration estimation was improved using a Gradient Boosting algorithm based on calculated DTW distances. This approach, which combines DTW for measuring similarity between time-series data points and Gradient Boosting for learning complex patterns, achieved high accuracy in predicting concentrations with limited training data.

In addition, several other features can be implemented in the classification algorithm (Cassisi et al. 2012; Rakthanmanon et al. 2012; Salvador and Chan, 2007; Shah et al., 2016), for analyzing even bigger datasets with more references and less computational power. Overall, this technique is useful for discriminating between different heavy metals in water, either alone or in a mixture. This is a new approach for understanding the bioluminescence kinetics of bacteria by analyzing their responses to environmental toxicants. This model needs to be constant with regard to temperature of analysis, medium for bacterial growth, and density of bacteria, since even the double distilled water had some variations in the bioluminescence kinetics (Uziel et al. 2024). Nevertheless, this did not prove to be an issue in the discrimination between copper and mercury. It is important to note that the medium used for growing the bacteria plays an important role, since different media affect the growth rate of bacteria in different ways, leading to different bioluminescence kinetics, also noted in the negative control test, which is a diluted medium. It is possible that toxicants other than copper and mercury will generate similar bioluminescence patterns. Therefore, it is recommended that a panel of bioluminescent bacteria with different promoters be used to identify toxic compounds more accurately.

A major concern when analyzing a complex matrix is how to deal with interferences. Although many toxicants can generate similar kinetics, the DTW algorithm can help in classifying those responses. Any bioluminescence kinetic that shows a high distance from a reference is interpreted as a different toxicant than those that have already been registered. This could help to better discriminate toxicants, even when their response ratios are similar. Another important aspect when trying to identify certain toxicants is the use of specific strains of bioluminescent bacteria with known promoters for individual heavy metals or toxicants of interest. In this way, it is the biological model that provides

a specific response, and further, the data can be interpreted for the estimation of concentration, creation of fingerprints, or detection of specific patterns. Finally, the combination of bioluminescent bacterial strains used in a panel can further enhance the discrimination of specific toxicants.

One limitation of our method is that all data were obtained using spiked DDW and not environmental water. Obviously, more work is required to adapt to such changes. Therefore, another limitation of the current dataset is that it may not fully capture the complexity of real environmental samples. Expanding the reference library with diverse representative references will improve the model capacity for accurate component identification and concentration estimation in complex mixtures. These new models would leverage multiple distance measurements derived from a wide array of references, which should improve the accuracy of concentration calculations in compounds, such as the Cu-Hg mixtures. Moreover, addressing the concern about the examples of Cu and Hg not fully capturing real-world toxicity complexities, our future work will aim to create solutions that incorporate the multifaceted nature of real toxicity scenarios. By acknowledging these limitations and explicitly aiming to enhance our approach, our study can evolve to represent real toxicological interactions more accurately.

The development of a larger dataset of references is an essential step in advancing our research approach, particularly in practical settings. In the era of big data, compiling such datasets has become a standard practice. Future work should incorporate this dataset to strengthen the practicality of our study, allowing us to assess and refine our methodologies more effectively. Currently, we are counting a limited set of references that include salts of Hg or Cu at fixed concentrations. This results in a highly nonlinear outcome when the concentration of a component in the mixture is determined. This presents an opportunity for further investigation, such as the development of a method to select appropriate references for each component. This task involves various data mining and (machine learning-based) feature selection techniques, such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA), random forest methods, or even state-of-the-art deep learning. By acquiring a larger and more diverse dataset of multi-references, we could develop a data-driven model capable of accurately calculating, for example, the concentration of Cu in the Cu-Hg compound based on multiple distances derived from several Cu references.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we propose a new method for deciphering bacterial bioluminescence as a recognition pattern for copper and mercury in binary mixtures in water, employing DTW as the underlying algorithm. By applying DTW to bioluminescence patterns, the similarity between different samples or conditions can be quantitatively assessed, and subtle variations in temporal dynamics can be detected, followed by the identification of specific features or time points associated with the effects of metal contaminants. DTW offers a flexible approach for analyzing bioluminescence data, allowing for accurate comparisons and pattern recognition, even in the presence of temporal distortions or variations in sequence length. By using DTW for pattern recognition, it is possible to better understand how different concentrations of copper and mercury affect the responses of bioluminescent bacteria over time. This could potentially lead to a more accurate system for the detection of heavy metals in water samples. By applying DTW to the resulting bioluminescence time series, distinct recognition patterns for copper and mercury were successfully deciphered, enabling the precise identification of each metal in the binary mixtures. Moreover, the DTW-based model demonstrated good accuracy in quantifying individual Cu and Hg concentrations, even when present in varying ratios. The proposed approach offers a new perspective for toxicity evaluation of environmental samples. Combining bioluminescent bacterial systems with DTW analysis is a reliable, cost-effective, and rapid tool for monitoring and

assessing toxic contaminants in water.

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Data access statement

All data related to this research may be found in our records in footprints (<https://footprints-b291f.web.app/>).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Calin Trif: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Son Quang Le:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jovana Vunduk:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Yardnapar Parcharoen:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Robert S. Marks:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.watres.2025.124230](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2025.124230).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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